

Strahlensatz

$g \parallel h \quad A_{\Delta} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \text{Basis} \cdot \text{Höhe}$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} |\Delta ABB'| &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{AB} \cdot h \\ |\Delta AA'B| &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{AB} \cdot h \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$|\Delta ABB'| = |\Delta AA'B|$$

$$|\Delta ABB'| = |\Delta AA'B| + |\Delta ZAB|$$

$$|\Delta ABB'| + |\Delta ZAB| = |\Delta AA'B| + |\Delta ZAB|$$

$$\frac{|\Delta ABB'|}{|\Delta ABB'|} + \frac{|\Delta ZAB|}{|\Delta ABB'|} = \frac{|\Delta AA'B|}{|\Delta AA'B|} + \frac{|\Delta ZAB|}{|\Delta AA'B|}$$

$$1 + \frac{|\Delta ZAB|}{|\Delta ABB'|} = 1 + \frac{|\Delta ZAB|}{|\Delta AA'B|} \quad | -1$$

I) $\frac{|\Delta ZAB|}{|\Delta ABB'|} = \frac{|\Delta ZAB|}{|\Delta AA'B|}$

$$\underbrace{|\Delta ABB'| + |\Delta ZAB|}_{|\Delta ZAB'|} = \underbrace{|\Delta AA'B| + |\Delta ZAB|}_{|\Delta ZA'B|}$$

⇒ II) $\frac{|\Delta ZAB|}{|\Delta ZAB'|} = \frac{|\Delta ZAB|}{|\Delta ZA'B|}$

$$\Rightarrow |\Delta ZAB| = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{zB} \cdot \overline{AC}$$

$$|\Delta ZAB| = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{zA} \cdot \overline{BD}$$

$$\Rightarrow |\Delta A'BB'| = \frac{1}{2} \overline{BB'} \cdot \overline{AC}$$

$$|\Delta AA'B'| = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{AA'} \cdot \overline{BD}$$

$$\text{ad I) } \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{zB} \cdot \overline{AC}}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{BB'} \cdot \overline{AC}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{zA} \cdot \overline{BD}}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{AA'} \cdot \overline{BD}}$$

$$\text{I') } \frac{\overline{zB}}{\overline{BB'}} = \frac{\overline{zA}}{\overline{AA'}}$$

$$\Rightarrow |\Delta zAB'| = \frac{1}{2} \overline{zB'} \cdot \overline{AC}$$

$$|\Delta z'A'B| = \frac{1}{2} \overline{z'A'} \cdot \overline{BD}$$

$$\text{ad II) } \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{zB} \cdot \overline{AC}}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{zB'} \cdot \overline{AC}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{zA} \cdot \overline{BD}}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot \overline{z'A'} \cdot \overline{BD}}$$

$$\text{II') } \frac{\overline{zB}}{\overline{zB'}} = \frac{\overline{zA}}{\overline{z'A'}}$$

$$\text{ad I') } \Rightarrow \frac{\overline{zB}}{\overline{zA}} = \frac{\overline{BB'}}{\overline{AA'}}$$

$$\text{ad II') } \Rightarrow \frac{\overline{zB}}{\overline{zA}} = \frac{\overline{zB'}}{\overline{z'A'}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\overline{zB}}{\overline{zB'}} = \frac{\overline{zA}}{\overline{z'A'}}$$

ΔzAB ist ähnlich zu $\Delta zA'B'$

$\Rightarrow$ wende Ähnlichkeitssatz an

$$\frac{\overline{zA'}}{\overline{zA}} = \frac{\overline{zB'}}{\overline{zB}} \quad ; \quad \frac{\overline{A'B'}}{\overline{AB}} = \frac{\overline{zA'}}{\overline{zA}} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\overline{zB'}}{\overline{zB}} = \frac{\overline{A'B'}}{\overline{AB}}$$